

Featured Article

Digital Governmentality: Technological Subjectivation and AI

Federico Jose T. Lagdameo
Ateneo de Naga University
Ateneo de Manila University
Polytechnic University of the Philippines

ABSTRACT*

This article develops a Foucauldian analysis of artificial intelligence technologies, particularly large language models such as ChatGPT, as contemporary technologies of power. Building upon Michel Foucault's genealogical critique of disciplinary and biopolitical regimes, it argues that AI systems instantiate new modes of subjectivation through algorithmic rationalities, predictive analytics, and interface designs that structure the conduct of users and the intelligibility of populations. These systems do not merely facilitate communication or automate tasks; they quietly shape behavior, organize possibilities for action, and determine what counts as truth or relevance in everyday life. AI thus functions as a digital apparatus of governmentality—disciplining individuals and regulating populations under the guise of neutrality and efficiency. By drawing out the continuities between modern technologies of power and today's intelligent systems, this paper seeks to denaturalize the present configuration of the digital subject and open the possibility for a renewed exercise of critique and freedom.

Keywords: Foucault, artificial intelligence, subjectivation, ChatGPT, LLMs, digital governmentality

Introduction

The phenomenon of artificial intelligence technologies such as Large Language Models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT is an impetus for the philosophical inquiry into the nature of subjectivity, agency, and freedom in the present time. Designed to assist users, optimize productivity, or enhance decision-making, these technological systems are generally construed as neutral tools of communication or computation. Nonetheless, their presence in education, governance, commerce, and socio-political life reveals a deeper and more troubling function: they participate in shaping human thought, conduct, and identity itself. What, then, are the philosophical stakes of living with—and through—artificial intelligence?

Now, most current approaches to artificial intelligence are either technical—concerned with its capabilities—or ethical—focused on issues such as fairness, transparency, or bias. Important as these are, they leave largely unexamined a prior and more fundamental issue: how AI functions as a technology of subjectivation. In other words, how do these systems quietly shape the ways individuals and populations think, speak, relate, and understand themselves?

The French philosopher, Michel Foucault, developed the analyses of disciplinary power and biopolitics that offer cogent conceptual tools that afford important insights on this matter. His genealogical investigations reveal how subjects have historically been constituted through institutional technologies—prisons, clinics, schools—and the subtle operations of knowledge and control. Today’s artificial intelligence systems, I argue, continue and reconfigure these operations. Hence, to understand AI philosophically requires such an analysis of how it participates in the formation of subjects and the conduct of conduct, beneath the surface of utility.

In this regard, I argue in this paper that artificial intelligence technologies such as ChatGPT instantiate a new modality of subjectivation that extends Foucault’s disciplinary and biopolitical logics. These technologies operate as contemporary technologies of power by regulating discourse, shaping behavioral norms, and aggregating population-level data, thereby producing a digitally governed subject that is docile, responsive, and intelligible through data. The seeming neutrality and ubiquity of AI systems conceal their constitutive effects on identity and agency, making a Foucauldian critique vital to understanding the political ontology of the digital self.

I begin with an extensive elaboration of Foucault’s account of disciplinary and biopolitical power and its construal of technologies of subjectivation. I then deploy these toward interrogating artificial intelligence systems as a technology of power that produces what may be termed as the digital subject. Finally, I

gesture towards the need for genealogical critique that allows for discursive space wherein the process of digital subjectivation is interrogated and resisted.

Foucault, Technologies of Power, and the Production of Subjects

It was through his genealogical analyses that Foucault developed a conception of power that was radically different from the “juridical model” that prevailed during his time. The said model conceived of power as “a right which can be possessed in the way one possesses a commodity, and which can therefore be transferred or alienated, either completely or partly, through a juridical act or an act that founds a right . . . thanks to the surrender of something or thanks to a contract.”¹ Foucault found this inadequate and sterile in contending with how “power” actually operates in the network of the social. Seeking a non-juridical model as an alternative, he explored what he called the “Reicheian” model and “Nietzschean” model for their feasibility.

These models, however, ultimately proved incapable of providing an account of how “power” operates. For one, Foucault remarked of being “suspicious” of the Reicheian model, or the notion that power is repression, because it stands mute when confronted by “the history of penal law, psychiatric power, controls on infantile sexuality, and so on . . . [since] the mechanisms at work in these power formations were something very different from—or at least much more than—repression.”² Commenting further that the repression model was “not really new”—having been articulated earlier by Hegel, then Freud, and later by Reich—Foucault turned to the Nietzschean model, that is, the notion that “[p]ower is war, the continuation of war by other means.”³ This resort, while not entirely satisfactory, eventually led Foucault to his own analytics of “power” or more precisely, “power relations.”

This was because what the Nietzschean model afforded Foucault was the cognizance of force relations in play in the happenstance of power. The analysis of the war hypothesis revealed the primacy of struggle and submission, and with it, the presupposition of parties exerting opposition on each other. The occurrence of power in this schema lies in those multiple and diverse oppositions—relations of force—that obtain or are exerted. Power, so understood, is a *relation* of force.

Nonetheless, Foucault asks: “To what extent can a relationship of domination [war] boil down to or be reduced to the notion of a relationship of force? To what extent and how can the relationship of force be reduced to a relationship of war? . . . Can war really provide a valid analysis of power-relations, and can it act as a matrix for techniques of domination?”⁴

Foucault had not been definitive with his own answers but insisted on specificity in deploying such a matrix. Thus, he maintained that the war

hypothesis, with its analytics of struggle, domination, and submission, is not inclusive enough. As he put it in one interview:

It just seems to me that the affirmation, pure and simple, of a “struggle” can’t act as the beginning and end of all explanations in the analysis of power-relations. This theme of struggle only really becomes operative if one establishes concretely—in each particular case—who is engaged in struggle, what the struggle is about, and how, where, by what means and according to what rationality it evolves. In other words, if one wants to take seriously the assertion that struggle is the core of relations of power, one must take into account the fact that the good old “logic” of contradiction is no longer sufficient, far from it, for the unravelling of actual processes.⁵

Dissatisfied but led on by the Nietzschean hypothesis, Foucault sought to make more precise the analytics of power as opposed to a metaphysics of it. In lieu of the latter which concerned itself with providing an answer to the questions of “what is power?” and “what are its properties?” (and was attached to the juridico-discursive model he was undermining); he undertook an analysis wherein power as such was not posited as an entity or substance. Rather, it focused on “relations of power” or “power-relations”: it focused on the questions of what happens in a relation of power, and on how power is exercised.

It was in this inquiry into the manner by, through, and in which power is exercised that we can detect in Foucault a construal of power, of obtaining power-relations, that is inextricably linked to technology. His specific analyses of power-relations reveal an account of technology that is directed towards social control, productive of knowledges and truths, and ultimately, formative of subjectivities.⁶

Remarking on his work on the history of penal practices as well as of sexuality, he notes the contrast of his conception of, as well as approach to the problem of power:

The case of the penal system convinced me that the question of power needed to be formulated not so much in terms of justice as in those of technology, of tactics and strategy, and it was this substitution for a judicial and negative grid of a technical and strategic one that I tried to effect in *Discipline and Punish* and then to exploit in “The History of Sexuality”.⁷

In another instance, he explains the importance of such a reformulation: “I think that we have to adopt the threefold point of view of the techniques, the

heterogeneity of techniques, and the subjugation-effects that make technologies of domination the real fabric of both power-relations and the great apparatuses of power. The manufacture of subjects rather than the genesis of the sovereign: that is our general theme.”⁸ His genealogical critique of technology, therefore, aimed at abetting the writing of a history of how the modern “self” had been constituted. Moreover, to comprehend how power-relations operate, Foucault recognized the need to view its imbrication with technologies that instantiate and enact them.

Now, what account of technology can be teased out of Foucault’s genealogical analyses? Foucault himself provides—again, rather retrospectively—a four-fold classification in terms of technology’s function:

- (1) technologies of production, which permit us to produce, transform, or manipulate things;
- (2) technologies of sign systems, which permit us to use signs, meanings, symbols, or signification;
- (3) technologies of power, which determine the conduct of individuals and submit them to certain ends or domination, an objectivizing of the subject;
- (4) technologies of the self, which permit individuals to effect by their own means or with the help of others a certain number of operations on their own bodies and souls, thoughts, conduct, and way of being, so as to transform themselves in order to attain a certain state of happiness, purity, wisdom, perfection, or immortality.⁹

Foucault added that what really exercised his interest, and as was evinced by his actual genealogical studies, were the third and the fourth types of technologies. He was keen to understand those technologies that subjected individuals—either by themselves or by others—and *subjectivized* them, that is, turned them into particular subjects. In this regard, Foucault construed technologies to have a subjectivizing function.

In fact, this is clear in Foucault’s depictions of technologies: they tended to dwell on their operation or functioning while steering away from any metaphysical account. This is not to say that he had no metaphysical presuppositions on the nature of technologies; only that he was not explicit about these. Regarding this, Steve Matthewman has argued that one can obtain an account of “technology” in the writings of Foucault, albeit one that is circumscribed by the definition from Science and Technology Studies (STS). For Matthewman, we can find in Foucault an operative typology of technology as “objects, practices, knowledge, and modes of organization.”

In “Foucault, Technology, and Actor-Network Theory,” Matthewman makes the case for Foucault’s importance to a strand of STS, namely Actor-Network Theory. There, Matthewman points to how the French thinker’s major

concepts are framed in technological terms, and how Foucault's targets for inquiry can be categorized according to STS's definition of technology as "objects, activities, knowledge, and modes of organization." Thus, Matthewman pointed to the stethoscope and the rifle in Foucault's *The Birth of the Clinic* and *Discipline and Punish* respectively as corresponding to the construal of technology as objects; to disciplinary and other techniques in *Discipline and Punish* and *History of Sexuality, Vol. I: An Introduction* as practices; to medical and penological discourses in *The Birth of the Clinic* and *Discipline and Punish* as knowledge; and to hospitals and prisons in the aforementioned works as modes of organization.¹⁰

Besides its function and typology, there is in Foucault's works a characterization of technology operating as instantiations and enactments of power-relations. To recall, Foucault defines *power* as "a set of actions on possible actions" or as "the conduct of conducts' and the management of possibilities," clarifying that it "exists only as exercised by some on others, only when it is put into action, even though [. . .] it is inscribed in a field of sparse available possibilities underpinned by permanent structures."¹¹ In other words, power as such only exists within a relational field, and pertains to actions that structure other actions in some particular manner. The structuring of the possibilities of actions, however, is enacted, instantiated, made operational by technologies either as objects (the stethoscope, the rifle), practices (disciplinary techniques), knowledge (medicine and penology), modes of organization (hospital, school, prison), or frequently, by the conglomeration of these. These technologies of power determine the possibilities of actions acted upon within the same relational field.

Foucault's celebrated analysis of Bentham's ingenious technological artefact discloses its imbrication with power:

[The Panopticon] arranges things in such a way that the exercise of power is not added on from the outside, like a rigid, heavy constraint, to the functions it invests, but is so subtly present in them as to increase their efficiency by itself increasing its own points of contact. The panoptic mechanism is not simply a hinge, a point of exchange between a mechanism of power and a function; it is a way of making power relations function in a function, and of making a function function through those power relations.¹²

In sum, Foucault's genealogical work developed a conception of power that rejected the juridical model dominant in his time—a model in which power was conceived as something held, exchanged, or imposed like a right or a possession. He insisted, instead, that power is not something one *has* but something that is *exercised* within a field of relations. This conception of power is relational, diffuse,

and immanent to social practices. Crucially, Foucault's shift from a metaphysics of power to an analytics of power allowed him to focus on how subjects are formed within specific historical constellations of knowledge, institutions, and technologies.

Now, in Foucault's oeuvre, there are two technologies of power which figured prominently in his genealogical writings, that of disciplinary technology and biopolitical technology or governmentality. These two operate as enactments and conduits of the determination and management of possibilities. Frequently mistaken to be conflated, these two technologies of power are distinct, albeit not mutually exclusive.

Foucault's lecture on 17 March 1976 is clarificatory in this regard:

From the eighteenth century onward (or at least at the end of the eighteenth century onward) we have, then, two technologies of power which were established at different times and which were superimposed. One technique is disciplinary; it centers on the body, produces individualizing effects, and manipulates the body as a source of forces that have to be rendered both useful and docile. And we also have a second technology which is centered not upon the body but upon life: a technology which brings together the mass effects characteristic of a population. [. . .] Both technologies are obviously technologies of the body [. . .] What is more, the two sets of mechanisms – one disciplinary and the other regulatory – do not exist at the same level. Which means of course that they are not mutually exclusive and can be articulated with each other.¹³

Briefly, disciplinary technologies, as he showed in *Discipline and Punish*, work by producing docile bodies through spatial arrangement, surveillance, schedules, and repetition. They render the body calculable and productive, not merely through repression but through subtle normalization. Meanwhile, biopolitical technologies which Foucault elaborated in *The History of Sexuality*, function at the level of populations, regulating birth, health, risk, and life itself. Both modes of power—disciplinary and biopolitical—do not simply repress but *produce* and *govern* specific kinds of subjectivity: the criminal, the patient, the deviant, the normal.

For instance, Foucault explains that a crucial component of the process of the production of subjects was the disciplinary technology which “discovered the body as object and target of power.”¹⁴ This technology rendered the body more knowable and analyzable, *and at the same time*, more useful for political and economic ends. In a word, they made the body *docile* for both knowing and

manipulation. This docile body constituted the *disciplined* individual, the modern subject. Foucault wrote of this in *Discipline and Punish*:

The human body was entering a *machinery of power* that explores it, breaks it down and rearranges it. A ‘political anatomy’, which was also a ‘mechanics of power’, was being born; it defined how one may have a hold over others’ bodies, not only so that they may do what one wishes, but so that they may operate as one wishes, with the techniques, the speed and the efficiency that one determines. Thus discipline produces subjected and practised bodies, ‘docile’ bodies.¹⁵ (*italics mine*)

Foucault explained further that to be “subjected” is to be the object of knowledge and simultaneously, to be the ground or foundation of that knowledge. It is to be a self whose identity is tied to being objectively comprehensible, not as object, but as subject. In other words, to be a subject is to have a relation to the self wherein knowledge and truth mediate that self-relation. It is to be a self whose identity is linked to supposed truths or knowledge about oneself.

Further still, he explains that “subjectivity” is one type of relationship to oneself that can be established; it is not the only kind of relationship one can have with oneself. As Foucault pointed out, “subjectivity . . . is of course only one of the given possibilities of organization of a self-consciousness.”¹⁶ Hence, subjectivity or to be a “subject” is only one form of identity the self can assume; this means there are other options in constituting the self’s identity.

Yet despite being only one of several possibilities, the self *as* subject has been the paradigm of the human sciences as they had endeavored to provide knowledge about ourselves. Hence according to Foucault, the self as subject has functioned as a “regime of truth” in which we have come to be constituted as human beings who *are* subjects.

Eventually, to be constituted as a subject is to be *governed* as a self whose behavior and thoughts are regulated by truths (think data or information) about oneself.

Governmentality or biopolitical power, Foucault stressed, was different from discipline: “Unlike discipline, which is addressed to bodies, the new nondisciplinary power is applied not to man-as-body but to the living man, to man as-living-being; ultimately, if you like, to man-as-species.”¹⁷ It was therefore not trained at the individualization of its objects, namely human bodies; rather, it enveloped the mass of individuals precisely as a totality to be managed beginning with their birth, development, up until their death. In a word, this distinct technology of power targeted not the individual body, but the

population. “Biopolitics deals with the population,” Foucault revealed, “with the population as political problem, as a problem that is at once scientific and political, as a biological problem and as power’s problem.”¹⁸

At its emergence in the eighteenth century, biopolitical technology dealt with the population by *regulating* and *securing* its biological processes: fertility, birth, longevity, illness, mortality. In so doing, it thereby structured the possibilities of the population’s actions: it effected *power* over them. Not in the manner dictated by disciplinary technology, however, but by “taking control of life and the biological processes of man-as-species and ensuring that they are not disciplined, but regularized.”¹⁹

This regulation of the population, as well as the installation of security, introduce[d] mechanisms with a certain number of functions that [were] very different from the functions of disciplinary mechanisms. The mechanisms introduced by biopolitics include[d] forecasts, statistical estimates, and overall measures. . . The mortality rate has to be modified or lowered; life expectancy has to be increased; the birth rate has to be stimulated. And most important of all, regulatory mechanisms must be established to establish an equilibrium, maintain an average, establish a sort of homeostasis, and compensate for variations within this general population and its aleatory field.”²⁰

What biopolitical technology, therefore, undertook was the *government* of the population, where Foucault’s employment of the term “government” hails from its usage and understanding during the sixteenth century. Then, it did not necessarily pertain to political structures or management of the state but rather indicated the manner in which the *conduct* of groups and individuals are to be ordered. Thus, “government” or more precisely, *governmentality* not only meant political or economic subjectation but also—and more importantly—the conduct of others’ conduct.

Foucault thus uncovered two technologies of power that developed wherein they subjected life to their machinations, allowing for the production of specific kinds of subjectivities or identities. These produced subjectivities, Foucault’s studies revealed, are more efficiently managed or controlled in the achievement of some economic and political ends. In fact, he indicated that the *discipline* of individuals and the *government* of peoples have produced the very identity that supposedly prevails in modernity, the “modern subject.” For Foucault, this is the “self” whose identity is governed by the *normative* binaries of the insane and the sane, the sick and the healthy, the delinquent and the law-abider, the heterosexual and the homosexual, the normal and the abnormal. And ultimately, by the norm of the true and the false, that is, by the truths about oneself.

Digital Governmentality and Artificial Intelligence

If the modern subject was shaped by disciplinary institutions—the prison, the school, the hospital—and later by biopolitical regimes concerned with regulating life itself, then arguably the contemporary subject find herself/himself increasingly configured by algorithmic systems. Artificial intelligence technologies, exemplified by large language model (LLM) systems such as ChatGPT, do not merely facilitate interaction; it constructs the very horizon of communicability and intelligibility. It configures what is sayable, what is desirable, what is askable. It does not simply process human input; it anticipates and normativizes it, forming subjects who are, to borrow Foucault’s phrase, “conducted in their conduct.”²¹

In its own description, ChatGPT depicts itself as a large language model developed by the business corporation, OpenAI. It is a sibling model to GPT-3 (Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3) and is designed for generating human-like text responses in a conversational context. ChatGPT has been trained on a diverse range of internet text and is capable of engaging in text-based conversations on a wide variety of topics.²²

As a technology, it is designed to understand and generate text in a conversational manner, in which it can answer questions, provide explanations, engage in small talk, and offer responses that mimic human-like conversation. Furthermore, since it can accept text and system-level instructions as inputs, this technology allows users to provide context or specify the desired behavior in a conversation, extending and expanding its application scenarios.

In their account, Slade and Ellis explain that LLMs such as ChatGPT “are trained on vast amounts of text data and are specifically designed to process and understand human language.” They add that ChatGPT was introduced to the public as an LLM generative AI tool in November of 2022 by OpenAI. They point out that ChatGPT “works like a chatbot, generating text responses to user-provided prompts. Users can request simple text responses or responses that are complex such as programming code, sonnets, entire essays, and mathematical theorems.”²³

Growing evidence indicates that AI technology such as ChatGPT is not a neutral tool.²⁴ It operates as a technology of power—seductive rather than coercive, adaptive rather than imposed. Drawing from Foucault’s analytics, the question is not so much whether AI thinks, but how it functions as a *dispositif*: a strategic assemblage of mechanisms for guiding conduct.²⁵ In the case of LLMs such as ChatGPT, its predictive capacities are built upon vast corpora of data sets, filtered and shaped by institutionalized judgments of relevance, propriety, and risk. What emerges is a mode of linguistic interaction governed by protocols

of appropriateness, learned through the machine but ultimately reflecting human, institutional, and commercial priorities.

Such systems discipline subtly: through interface design, behavioral nudges, feedback loops, and the quiet promise of efficiency. The user is not coerced but formed—taught not only how to speak, what to expect, and how to remain within the bounds of the platform. But, more perniciously perhaps, the user is taught how to think, how to be a particular self: a digital subject.²⁶

Simultaneously, AI operates biopolitically. Its logic is not merely communicative but statistical. It aggregates, profiles, predicts. The value of AI systems lies in their capacity to render populations intelligible and actionable—not for the sake of human flourishing, but in service of operational efficiency, profit, and control.²⁷

In operating as such, AI technology masks its power as convenience. For AI is not experienced as surveillance, but as assistance. It looms not as an institution with enclosures, but functions as an ambient presence embedded in everyday digital life. Shoshana Zuboff portrayed this condition as characteristic of the era of “surveillance capitalism,” where behavioral data is continuously extracted and commodified.²⁸ The human subject engaging AI technology is thus not simply the user of a tool. Rather, s/he is the product of its protocols—a subject who is increasingly docile, data-generative, and governable.

Hence, from Foucault’s genealogical lens, artificial intelligence technology does not merely generate text, images, or decisions. It generates subjects.²⁹ Not in the juridical or even the existential sense, but in the Foucauldian sense of subjectivation: the process by which individuals are constituted through and within relations of power.³⁰

In fact, the “AI user” is doubly subjected. First, by the disciplinary mechanisms that normalize interaction—timing responses, shaping tone, ranking relevance. Second, by the biopolitical rationalities that convert lives into datasets, individuals into statistical aggregates, and experiences into marketable insights.³¹ This subject is no longer the Cartesian ego—sovereign, autonomous, self-transparent—but the digital subject: fragmentary, recursive, modulated through continuous feedback, and legible only insofar as it can be parsed by algorithms.

It is a transformation that comes at a significant cost.

For not only does one’s privacy or autonomy that hangs in a balance in this transformation. More crucially, it is also that deeper moral relation to the self—the capacity to pose questions to oneself that are not already shaped by the logic

of optimization. In a world governed by AI mediation, one's identity risks becoming less a matter of becoming and more a matter of formatting.

Toward a Genealogical Critique of AI

In his "Introduction" to an anthology of Foucault's work on power, James Faubion notes that "[o]ne of the messages of Foucault's [work] is . . . that the apparent neutrality and political invisibility of techniques of power is what makes them dangerous."³² Technologies of power are dangerous because their operations, i.e., their production of particular identities or selves, their *subjection* of individuals, are unseen even as they are placed in plain view of their subjects. What technologies of power do to us, to paraphrase Foucault, "is dangerous, which is not the same as bad."³³ Their danger lies primarily in their *invisibility* in the production of the identities, rendering them resistant to critiques often mounted on the platform of human rights or variants of humanist values.

To critique artificial intelligence technologies, then, is not simply to call for more ethical algorithms, or for greater transparency in the design of systems. Such efforts assume the standpoint of the Cartesian subject who relates to reality as its epistemic and political sovereign. More dangerously, this standpoint views technology as value-neutral instruments devoid of any agency, and hence, engenders the illusion of their complete control by human inventors and users.³⁴

Instead, what is required is the undertaking of genealogical critique of AI technology—a critical history of the present that refuses to accept the digital subject as inevitable and hence, normative and natural. Such a genealogical critique seeks to uncover the contingent rationalities—technical, economic, governmental—that have given rise to the current configuration of AI and its shaping of subjectivity. It asks: What desires, what fears, have we internalized, such that we now long for digital tools that anticipate us, guide us, and gently constrain us? What modes of resistance, what counter-practices, might still be possible within these digitally governed spaces?

To speak of freedom here is not to fantasize about a world without technology, but to recover the possibility of thinking otherwise—of reclaiming a moral relation to the self that is not reducible to algorithmic calibration. It is to insist that the subject of AI, while made, need not be final.

What is ultimately at stake in the rise of artificial intelligence is not merely human uniqueness or ethical safeguards, but the very condition of freedom. Not freedom as independence from power, but freedom as the capacity to constitute oneself otherwise—amid and through power. The digital self, as produced by AI technology, is governed through norms that masquerade as utility, through designs that mask subjection with convenience.³⁵

Foucault's insight is that power is not merely repressive but productive. The danger posed by technologies of power such as AI systems deployed as LLMs is that their production of identities, that is, the process of subjectivation, frequently escapes concern much less critical scrutiny of the formed subjects. This production of subjectivity through unseen yet ubiquitous mechanisms is what renders these technologies dangerous. They operate not from outside the subject, but through the internalization of norms, the organization of possibilities, and the formatting of desires. Consequently, these technologies of power establish hegemonic subject identities shielded from critique.

The task, then, is not to escape power, but to resist its totalization. This resistance begins in thought, in critique, in the refusal to accept as natural and normal what is in fact the effect of historical contingencies and strategic, technical, but non-subjective designs. As Foucault wrote:

[T]he things which seem most evident to us are always formed in the confluence of encounters and chances, during the course of a precarious and fragile history. . . . It means that they reside on a base of human practice and human history; and that since these things have been made, they can be unmade, as long as we know how it was that they were made.³⁶

And this is the role of philosophical thought today: to confront not only the enormous fascisms that threaten our shared life, but also the quiet ones—the algorithmic, polite, efficient fascisms that govern our everyday. AI is neither the enemy nor a neutral tool. It is a site—perhaps the site—where the struggle for freedom and for our identity must now be thought and contested anew.

Notes

¹ Michel Foucault, *Society Must Be Defended: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1975-1976*, ed. Mauro Bertani and Alessandro Fontana, trans. David Macey (New York: Picador, 2003), 13. Henceforth cited as *SMD*.

² *SMD* 18.

³ *SMD* 15.

⁴ *SMD* 46.

⁵ Michel Foucault, "The Eye of Power" in *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977*, ed. Colin Gordon, trans. Colin Gordon, Leo Marshall, John Mepham, and Kate Soper (New York: Pantheon Books, 1980), 164.

⁶ "The main objective . . . is to attack not so much such-or-such institution of power, or group, or elite, or class but, rather, a technique, a form of power. . . . that applies itself to immediate everyday life categorizes the individual, marks him by his own individuality, attaches him to his own identity, imposes a law of truth on him that he must recognize and others have to recognize in him. It is a form of power that makes

individuals subjects. There are two meanings of the word “subject”: subject to someone else by control and dependence, and tied to his own identity by a conscience or self-knowledge. Both meanings suggest a form of power that subjugates and makes subject to.” See Michel Foucault, “The Subject and Power,” in *The Essential Works of Foucault, 1954–1984, Volume 3: Power*, ed. James D. Faubion, trans. Robert Hurley (New York: The New Press, 2001), 331.

⁷ Michel Foucault, “The History of Sexuality” in *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977*, ed. Colin Gordon, trans. Colin Gordon, Leo Marshall, John Mepham, and Kate Soper (New York: Pantheon Books, 1980), 184.

⁸ *SMD* 46.

⁹ Michel Foucault, “Technologies of the Self,” in *Technologies of the Self*, ed. L. Martin, H. Gutman, and P. Hutton (Amherst: The University of Massachusetts Press, 1988), 18. Henceforth cited as *TS*.

¹⁰ Steve Matthewman, “Foucault, Technology, and Actor-Network Theory” in *Techné: Research in Philosophy and Technology*, 17:2 (Spring 2013): 276.

¹¹ Foucault, “The Subject and Power,” 340-341.

¹² *DP*, 206-207.

¹³ *SMD* 249, 250.

¹⁴ *DP* 136.

¹⁵ *DP* 138.

¹⁶ Michel Foucault, “The Return to Morality” in *Politics, Philosophy, Culture: Interviews and Other Writings, 1977-1984*, ed. Lawrence D. Kritzman (New York: Routledge, 1988), 253.

¹⁷ *SMD* 243.

¹⁸ *SMD* 245.

¹⁹ *SMD* 246-247.

²⁰ *SMD* 246.

²¹ Michel Foucault, *Security, Territory, Population: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1977–78*, ed. Michel Senellart, trans. Graham Burchell (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007), 192.

²² OpenAI, ‘What are large language models? What is ChatGPT?’, ChatGPT by OpenAI, last modified September 24, 2023, <https://chat.openai.com/c/09164395-5a26-4312-bbd6-aaa4d3166499>

²³ Amanda R. Ellis & Emily Slade, “A New Era of Learning: Considerations for ChatGPT as a Tool to Enhance Statistics and Data Science Education,” *Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education*, 31:2, 128-133, DOI: 10.1080/26731616.2023.2223601.

²⁴ See the 2025 MIT study by Nataliya Kosmyna et al, “Your Brain on ChatGPT: Accumulation of Cognitive Debt when Using an AI Assistant for Essay Writing Task,” arXiv, 2025, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2506.08872v1>.

See also John Nosta, “AI and the Arrival of the Cognitive Colonizers” in *Psychology Today*, 17 July 2025, <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/the-digital-self/202507/ai-and-the-arrival-of-the-cognitive-colonizers>.

²⁵ Foucault, *Security, Territory, Population*, 119–120.

²⁶ It is in this regard that Luciano Floridi’s claim regarding humanity’s transformation into “inforgs,” brought on by what he heralded as the Fourth Revolution becomes even more cogent and striking. For Floridi, the immense developments in information and communication technology together with their intensive societal uptake created a new space to which humanity is migrating, the infosphere. It is this migration, in turn, which is transforming humanity to a new type of self, a subject that is an informational organism, or inforg. See Luciano Floridi, *The Fourth Revolution: How the Infosphere is Reshaping Human Reality* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014), 98.

²⁷ Antoinette Rouvroy and Thomas Berns, trans. Elizabeth Libbrecht, “Algorithmic Governmentality and Prospects of Emancipation,” *Réseaux* 177, no. 1 (2013): 173.

²⁸ Shoshana Zuboff, *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power* (New York: PublicAffairs, 2019).

²⁹ It is worth pointing out that while Foucault has been known to be critical of the Cartesian subject and the philosophy of the subject that emerged from it; what is not widely discussed is how his notion of power-relations is itself a critique of the Cartesian ontology of the detached, disembodied, ahistorical, rational subject. In positing that power exists only within a relational field, and that “power is everywhere,” or that there is no “outside” to power, Foucault was not claiming how trapped we are by it as is misconstrued by some critics like Habermas, Fraser, Taylor, and others. Rather, he pointed to how our existences are thoroughly social and relational. What he was indicating—contra Descartes—was a different point of departure in studying ourselves: not as atomized individuals but as belonging to a network or web of relations.

³⁰ Foucault, “The Subject and Power,” 326–348.

³¹ Rouvroy and Berns, “Algorithmic Governmentality,” 175–178.

³² James D. Faubion, “Introduction” to *Power: Essential Works of Foucault, 1954-1984*, vol. 3, ed. James D. Faubion, trans. Robert Hurley and others (New York: The New Press, 2000), xv.

³³ Foucault, “On the Genealogy of Ethics, 256.

³⁴ Elsewhere, I develop the argument and view that technology possesses non-human agency.

³⁵ Nick Couldry and Ulises A. Mejias, *The Costs of Connection: How Data Is Colonizing Human Life and Appropriating It for Capitalism* (Redwood, CA: Stanford University Press,

2019).

³⁶ Michel Foucault, “Structuralism and Post-structuralism” in *Aesthetics, Method, and Epistemology: Essential Works of Foucault, 1954-1984*, vol. 2, ed. James D Faubion, trans. Robert Hurley and others (New York: The New Press, 1998), 450.

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